

NERC
Environmental
Data Service

Sharing highlights from the Environmental Data Service at the NERC Digital Gathering 2025

A deliverable report for the AMPLIFY-EDS project

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Contents

Context	2
About the Environmental Data Service	3
About the project	3
About the NERC Digital Gathering.....	4
What we did.....	5
Exhibition stand	6
Workshop.....	8
Hackathon support	14
Lessons learnt and recommendations	15
For EDS.....	15
For event organisers	17
Next steps and recommendations	18
For EDS.....	18
For event organisers	18
Annex A – session details	19
Talk: Highlights from the NERC Environmental Data Service	20
Workshop: Shaping the Future of AI-Ready, User-Driven Environmental Data	21
Exhibition stand	22
References	23

Context

The purpose of this report is to:

- Provide a citeable output from the AMPLIFY-EDS project
- Inform future EDS direction based on feedback, lessons learnt and discussions with users
- Inform NERC Digital Gathering event organisers of lessons learnt from the perspective of the EDS

About the Environmental Data Service

The [Environmental Data Service](#) (EDS) provides a focal point for scientific data and information spanning all environmental science domains: atmosphere and climate, earth observation, polar and cryosphere, marine, terrestrial and freshwater, geoscience, solar and space physics. The EDS is made up of a network of distributed data centres, with domain specific expertise.

Our main goal is to ensure that environmental data are made available, accessible and re-usable for the long-term in order to fully realise their value. We are funded by the [Natural Environment Research Council \(NERC\)](#), part of [UK Research and Innovation](#), to advise researchers on how to prepare data for long term storage and dissemination.

The EDS is a fundamental part of [NERC's digital strategy](#) and works with the [Digital Solutions Hub](#), and other partners, to break down disciplinary barriers and facilitate data sharing beyond academic use.

About the project

The AMPLIFY-EDS project was funded by the UKRI DRI Phase II call. It ran from March 2024 to Oct 2025.

Within this project, the EDS developed an end-to-end sensor workflow to demonstrate elements of an EDS data commons framework - initiating the first elements in the data commons roadmap. It delivered live data from several research sensor sources through a common workflow and demonstrated their use within shared tools.

AMPLIFY had two primary aims:

- To co-design and develop a live-data prototype service that delivers environmental sensor data and its associated metadata in a standardised, end-to-end workflow.

- To engage with peer sensor data initiatives and stakeholders across the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) and beyond, ensuring alignment, interoperability, and community input.

This work builds upon previous work undertaken via the [ENHANCE](#) and [BOOST](#) projects.

About the NERC Digital Gathering

[The 2025 NERC Digital Gathering](#) was held between the 7th-9th October and hosted by [Cranfield University](#) and the [National Centre for Atmospheric Science](#). The event, with 170 attendees, brought together the research community to highlight the increasing role of digital technologies and innovation in environmental science. The programme included the outcomes from NERC funded research programmes, the ongoing work of the [Environmental Data Service](#) and a forward look toward new funding opportunities and planned investments. Four key themes were covered: next-generation sensing, data science tools and techniques, enhancing data services, pioneering computation science.

The three-day schedule included keynotes from digital innovation leaders within both industry and the policy community, themed sessions, presentations, lightning talks and poster sessions. This included contributions on next-generation sensing ([Satellite Applications Catapult](#)), the development of the [National Underground Asset Register \(Atkins-Realis\)](#), enhancing data services ([BioFAIR](#)) and pioneering computation science ([Amazon Web Services](#)). It also included workshops on shaping the future of AI-ready, user-driven environmental data – and user-testing for the [Digital Solutions Hub](#).

Attendees came from over 40 different organisations, including universities, NERC research centres, consultancies, charities and private companies.

The 2026 Digital Gathering will be hosted on the 8th-10th September by the University of Stirling.

The Digital Gathering is an important annual event where we can share recent work, gather feedback and ideas from the community, and showcase progress to our funders.

Work to enhance our services has been undertaken via additional project funding. One such project is [the AMPLIFY project](#) - which was one of the key driving forces for successful EDS representation at this year's event (including covering a shortfall in the events finances and membership on the organising committee). To accurately and clearly describe recent work, it was decided that specific projects would not be described at the event – instead, a coherent narrative would cover all enhancement work undertaken over the last few years.

Image: event attendees at the 2025 NERC Digital Gathering at Cranfield University

What we did

Three key activities were undertaken to provide a coherent picture of the EDS:

- Talk (40 mins) = ‘Highlights from the NERC Environmental Data Service’
- Workshop (1.5 hours) = ‘Shaping the Future of AI-Ready, User-Driven Environmental Data’
- Exhibition stand (during networking sessions)

Other representation included:

- Over 30 EDS staff attended the event, ranging from early career data experts to heads of data infrastructure. Purposes for attending ranged from delivering talks, workshops and posters, to acting as a representative for the early careers network. Individuals were supported to attend via multiple funding routes: core EDS funding, AMPLIFY, JASMIN, FDRI, ATLANTIS.
- Hackathon support by JASMIN/CEDA staff
- Posters and talks about specific work (by staff linked to the EDS)

The workshop was a key deliverable as defined within the AMPLIFY project, but all sessions were necessary to help disseminate the work and gather feedback from as many attendees as possible.

A summary of the exhibition stand, workshop, and hackathon are below. See Annex A for further details (including links to presentation slides).

Exhibition stand

The exhibition stand consisted of pull up banners, leaflets, a rolling slide deck on a laptop, and interactive feedback posters. During all networking sessions, at least one member of EDS staff was available at the exhibition stand to answer questions and encourage attendees to provide feedback.

Image: the new branded pull up banner created for the EDS exhibition stand

The figures below are digitised versions of the feedback collected throughout the event via the exhibition stand. Figure 1 shows quantitative information using sticky dots to indicate answers, Figures 2 and 3 shows qualitative feedback collected via post it notes about data challenges and our roadmap objectives.

Figure 1: feedback collected on an interactive poster at the exhibition stand using sticky dots

Figure 2: post it notes containing feedback about data challenges, themed into six key areas; sustainable funding and resources, data culture and engagement, access and paywalls, APIs and technical simplicity, documentation and usability.

Figure 3: post it notes containing feedback related to the five roadmap objectives; governance and management, user engagement, innovation, training, service delivery and data governance.

Workshop

The workshop aimed to provide:

- Overview of new proof-of-concept services
- Opportunity for requirements gathering, feedback and discussion to shape the future of data services
- Delve into the details with our team
- Identify opportunities for future collaboration

The format of the workshop consisted of slides, discussion and feedback. The work was introduced in a short 10 minute presentation and then the remainder of the workshop was informal discussion with participants moving between different ‘stations’ (see Figure 4).

Description of the stations

Station 1 Data in	Station 2 A look under the hood	Station 3 End user applications	Station 4 AI readiness	Station 5 Feedback and next steps
<p>Demonstration - how to add sensor data into the service</p> <p>What data services do decisions makers need for cross-sector environmental challenges in line with Government missions?</p> <p>Where would you like this work to go? What other data to add? e.g. FDRI</p> <p>Louise, Sam, James, Faiza</p>	<p>Demonstration - how to consume sensor data from the service via a Jupyter notebook</p> <p>Demonstration - interactive map</p> <p>SensorThingsAPI & UI</p> <p>The Building Blocks</p> <p>How do you wish you could combine, access and analyse data from multiple sources or across disciplines?</p> <p>Alex, Colm, Andy, Helen</p>	<p>Demonstration - AI tool for data access and visualisation</p> <p>What new tools and techniques are emerging?</p> <p>Where should we focus efforts?</p> <p>How can we best ensure users can discover, pick up and use new resources/services?</p> <p>Carl, Paulius</p>	<p>What are the 'high value' datasets for your community?</p> <p>What are your barriers to getting started with Machine Learning?</p> <p>Can we build safe and trustworthy AI agents?</p> <p>How can we build environmental Foundation Models?</p> <p>Ag, Mike</p>	<p>Capturing missing user stories</p> <p>Would you like to collaborate with us in future projects?</p> <p>How can we improve the EDS roadmap to suit your needs?</p> <p>How have you found the workshop?</p> <p>Poppy, Jesse</p>

Figure 4: description of the stations available during the workshop, covering five themes; data in, a look under the hood, end user applications, AI readiness, feedback and next steps.

The workshop received strong engagement and positive interactions throughout the session – with over 30 attendees joining. We received good feedback about the work – there was high interest but limited outside of the EDS group. Good discussions about integrating with the EDS Commons, though as this work is still a prototype future planning needed.

Key themes discussed at each station are summarised below.

Station 1 – data in

- Positive feedback about the approaches used
- Several new connections made via the workshops and have had continued discussions (details below)
- [FDRI](#) discussions about interest in the communication protocols used e.g. Met Office, EO data hub. Topics covered included:
 - Barriers in existing landscape, pros and cons
 - If MQTT is the future of new sensors? Or proprietary tools?
 - Feedback from FDRI (using mixed approach)
 - Next steps: reach out to Met Office about use of AWS and egress services (specifically for sensors)
 - Next steps: SAWiE network keen to know more about FDRI – follow up with them <https://sawie.net/>
- Researcher from Northumbria University very interested in the pilot service and would potentially like to trial integrating their sensors with our system.
 - Low energy sensors (with 4G connectivity) in remote arctic locations
 - They're at the beginning of their project, so a good external use case to explore integrating with the system
 - Next steps: keep having these conversations and explore opportunities for funding to support the work going forwards

Station 2 – a look under the hood

- General acceptance that our proposed solution was solving a real user problem/need
- They wanted: improved data access, clear machine-readable input sources, consistency of data and metadata
- The demo notebook received well – couple of minor difficulties (typos, one data stream that didn't run)
- Discussion about analogous problems and could see benefit in following our approach for tackling their issues
- Discussion with a university researcher in geosciences who was interested in mapping across to other environmental informatics disciplines
- Pointed people at EDS webpages and data centre webpages
 - It would have been useful to have a webpage to point to (a centralised place where project outputs are summarised and linked to)
- Engaged with [PML](#) – they want to implement the same solution
 - Next steps: continue discussions with PML
- There has been international interest with [OGC](#) (outside of the workshop)

- This highlighted the value for our approach for supplying data and tools that meet an underlying community need. More widespread community engagement is needed to identify priority datatypes or future provision for maximising their uptake.

Station 3 – end user applications

- Mainly spoke to NERC affiliated people (e.g. mix of research centre and data centre staff)
- (As expected,) no one cared about the specific project outputs, cared more about the big picture and shared challenges
- General interest and agreement with proposals of what we do next (in terms of lowering the barriers to access)
 - the way we focus on onboarding materials seemed sensible
 - documentation/training/comms and engagement was all necessary and appropriate
 - involving users in more stages of design and development (people don't know where to start with this)
 - important to do user research (but people don't know how to do this)
- There was particular interest in:
 - [Co-creation Toolkit](#) (using and contributing)
 - NCP and AI (general interest in the possibilities)
 - How to find users (especially those that you don't know)
- There were no major new revelations/insights
- Our understanding of the target audience is generally seen as correct,
 - Next steps: follow up with volunteers for toolkit e.g. NOC presentation/examples, Northumbria Uni cocreating with indigenous communities, BODC ingest app
- Discussed Large Language Models (LLMs) – demoed how APIs for external data sources can be connected. Not many people are using this way of working yet but there was interest to learn more.
 - Next steps: explore using natural language for exploring documentation/training resources
- Lecture theatre and workshops prompted ideas for what to do next with the research insights we have. What was described is very close to what NOC has already got, so she could expand and develop this for wider EDS

Station 4 – AI readiness

- Foundation Models (FMs) and AI Techniques

- Use of third-party image-based FMs (e.g., DynoV2, SAM) for environmental applications.
- Fine-tuning and transfer learning:
 - Adding new model heads for segmentation.
 - Combining expert-labelled data with self-supervised learning.
- Challenges:
 - Cost and computational resource requirements (GPUs, VRAM).
 - Accuracy trade-offs and environmental impact.
- Use cases:
 - Woodland change analysis.
 - High-resolution drone imagery combined with Sentinel-2 data.
 - Infilling and downscaling techniques.
- High-Value Datasets
 - Importance of multi-species datasets for labelling and training.
 - Data scarcity for large-scale development planning (energy, housing).
 - Drone/UAV data as a low-cost solution for data collection.
 - Consultancies aggregating free NERC and other datasets into GIS systems.
 - Need for trust and accessibility across sectors when sharing data and models.
- Guidance and Documentation
 - FAIR principles: Difficulty in repeating and verifying research workflows.
 - Lack of clear documentation and guidance for:
 - Resource requirements (e.g., GPUs for specific models).
 - Workflow reproducibility.
 - Suggested solutions:
 - Flowcharts and detailed user support.
 - Helpdesk chatbots with contextual guidance.
- Responsible AI Use
 - AI as an assistant, not a replacement for human expertise.
 - Environmental and financial cost considerations:
 - Trade-offs between model accuracy and resource consumption.
 - Need for tools to inform decisions about local vs remote AI use.
 - Efficiency improvements (e.g., latency reduction) to minimise resource use.
- User Needs and Accessibility
 - Different users require tailored solutions and resources.
 - Cross-sector accessibility and trust are critical.
 - Improving ease of evaluation for data and models.

Station 5 – feedback and next steps

- Generally found it difficult to get overall feedback from workshop attendees as they were more interested in speaking to the other stations
- Some broad topics discussed:
 - Are we reaching the right people?
 - How can we connect with users beyond our communities? - It's great to have these meetings, but should we be attending events & meeting people outside of environmental science? E.g. lawyers, architects, and insurance or health sectors.
 - Everyone already gets loads of surveys in their inbox, how can we encourage people to take time to tell us their needs?
 - How do we ensure we follow up on potential collaboration opportunities (identified at the event) when funding/time is limited? How to prioritise? How to keep track of these interactions?
 - How can we encourage more opportunities to collaborate with the other datacentres in our regular day-to-day work?
 - We could make more of an effort to encourage discussions and collaborations e.g. inviting people to internal training sessions which would be relevant to all the data centres or holding informal discussion/brainstorming sessions.
 - Do we utilise our existing communication platforms enough? E.g. the EDS Slack.

Image: lively discussions at the workshop covered five topics; data in, a look under the hood, end user applications, AI readiness, next steps and feedback.

Hackathon support

[The hackathon materials](#) demonstrated the use of CEDA data (one of the data centres which is part of the EDS) using JASMIN notebooks. It was great that the hackathon materials were created by a member of the research community (not a member of CEDA staff). However, we'd like to note that they are also slightly limited in the approach that was taken. Due to late involvement of CEDA staff, we were unable to help shape the content that was delivered. Multiple CEDA/JASMIN staff were available during the hackathon to offer support to attendees.

If we had been involved earlier, we would have suggested the following ideas:

- Finding data in the CEDA Catalogue then transitioning to reading files in the CEDA archive
- Using the data remotely (i.e. running on Google Colab or somewhere similar) - reading data over HTTPS/OpenDAP
- Using our STAC catalogue
- Providing guidelines on building data loaders (rather than hard-coding file paths)

For future resources, it might be interesting to ask individuals to consider the points above and work on creating notebooks (as documentation) for how to do this. We would like to better integrate future hackathons with the wider EDS.

Lessons learnt and recommendations

For EDS

Positive

- EDS representation on the event organising committee was helpful
- Joining an existing event was helpful as it was a captive audience
- The audience were interested in the work we presented
- The station format for the workshop seemed to work well with many positive conversations
- Having presence in various ways across the conference allowed more interactions and feedback to be gathered (rather than just via the workshop as was originally planned)
- Gathering details of EDS staff attending was helpful for coordinating sessions and networking purposes
- Early career researchers had positive experiences. Hannah Revett, who attended the conference as a representative of the EDS early careers network

said: "After seeing a range of talks and presentation styles at the NERC Digital Gathering I came away feeling like presenting a poster or presentation at a future event no longer seemed like an impossible task. It was most interesting to see the trends across separate organisations within digital environmental science as well as where developments seem to be heading - I felt as if this put the work I do into a wider context. Talking to a range of people who were all at different career stages gave a clearer sense of what parts of the field excite me and highlighted areas to learn more about. I was also able to make face-to-face connections with people who I have only worked with via email which broke the ice for future communications. Overall, the NERC DG was a really good insight into conference events from an early careers perspective, and I would definitely encourage other early careers professionals to attend in the future."

Neutral

- During the workshop, the fire alarm at the venue went off. Resulting in delays to the schedule and a room swap being required
- It was difficult to get feedback from people at the workshop (no one really spoke to the dedicated feedback station and other stations didn't take notes) - this was exacerbated by the fire alarm issues
- Unable to explore in detail who was in the workshop (as limited interaction with the feedback station) - Were the right people in the room? Did we speak to 'enough' people?
- Designing and running a hackathon is a requirement on the High 5 for AI project within 12 months of the project end.
 - o Suggestion: Project team should learn from the challenges noted in this report. Decision required whether to commit and use the 2026 Digital Gathering to fulfil this requirement (and speak to organisers early about putting this in the schedule)

Negative

- Organiser did not inform us the hackathon would be based on EDS data until a few weeks before. Resulting in the resources following a slightly limited approach.
- Cost of attendance (and logistics of paying for it with UKRI restrictions) restricted the number of staff available to attend. More individuals wanted to attend but funding restraints limited this.
 - o Suggestion: discuss how representation can be fairly distributed across teams each year

- Suggestion: run an online webinar to re-run the EDS sessions (e.g. talk and workshop) and to share key takeaways from those who did attend. Consider whether to open this out to non-EDS people too
- Whilst the workshop was well attended, it consisted of lots of people who already knew what we were doing. It is hard to know the level of detail to pitch it at to get people engaged and wanting to attend the session.
 - Suggestion: get technical team to go out and specifically invite people in their wider networks to attend the workshop.
 - Suggestion: ask event organisers to collect more information about the types of people registering so we can tailor content presented

For event organisers

Positive

- EDS representation on the event organising committee was helpful
- It provided distributed EDS staff with opportunities to network and collaborate in person

Neutral

- Shortfall in event finances were covered by an offer from the AMPLIFY project
 - Suggestion: for future events, ask projects in advance for funding support. We found it a useful mechanism for project delivery. It would have been good to plan this in to project costs earlier.
- Lack of organiser representation in smaller rooms. It needed someone to introduce speakers and encourage questions
 - Suggestion: ensure all parallel sessions have been assigned someone to chair. Ask members of the community to support – EDS staff would be willing to help.
- It would be nice to have more focus on networking for early careers attendees
 - Suggestion: think about a dedicated early careers session
- There was a lot of presentations, would have liked more discussion sessions
 - Suggestion: more panel/fireside chat discussions

Negative

- Late programme publication and acceptance of abstracts caused confusion and frustration amongst presenters
 - Suggestion: close abstract submissions earlier than the registration deadline to allow programme to be published further in advance
 - Suggestion: review and accept/decline abstracts (rather than accepting all of them). Ask members of the organising committee to support.

- Hackathon was too late in the evening, so numbers were very limited
 - o Suggestion: schedule hackathon in main programme
- Hackathon in main lecture theatre was not conducive to collaborative working
 - o Suggestion: host future hackathons in smaller rooms with cabaret style tables
- There was confusion in timings of the sessions on day 2 due to previous sessions overrunning. People had been told different things by the event organisers.
 - o Suggestion: decide how to deal with delays ahead of the event and ensure consistent messages are communicated to attendees (especially when there are sessions running in parallel)
- Cost of attendance (and logistics of paying for it with UKRI restrictions) restricted the number of EDS staff available to attend. More individuals wanted to attend but funding restraints limited this.
 - o Suggestion: ask NERC funded projects to contribute some funding to the event (e.g. like the AMPLIFY project did) - allowing registration price to be reduced
- Parallel sessions clashed with other talks that were in the same theme e.g. our workshop clashed with EDRUK talk.
 - o Suggestion: parallel sessions should be from different themes to reduce the risk of clashes for people
- Abstracts weren't prominent/visible on the website for people to understand what sessions to attend
 - o Suggestion: add abstracts into the programme so it is easier to quickly see what each session is about

Next steps and recommendations

For EDS

- This report to be circulated and discussed with EDS management (via the Data Operations Group). EDS management should share with their appropriate team members.
- EDS management to ensure feedback/recommendations are actioned via appropriate mechanisms (e.g. via a roadmap implementation plan)
- EDS management to ensure progress is reported at next Digital Gathering (e.g. last year you said, this year we did X in response)

For event organisers

- This report to be circulated and discussed with the event organising committee

- Organising committee to ensure feedback/recommendations are actioned for the next Digital Gathering

Annex A – session details

Three abstracts were submitted:

- Talk = ‘Highlights from the NERC Environmental Data Service’
- Workshop = ‘Shaping the Future of AI-Ready, User-Driven Environmental Data’
- Exhibition stand = ‘Environmental Data Service exhibition stand’

See descriptions below (including links to slides and additional resources where relevant). These sessions were coordinated by an EDS staff member who was also on the organising committee for the event – ensuring consistent and clear messages were communicated at the event.

Talk: Highlights from the NERC Environmental Data Service

Authors: Patrick Bell, Louise Darroch, Ag Stephens, Poppy Townsend, Carl Watson

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17495167>

Recording: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Kf-ZqSddFWhbHyBt9fIHt4DXFwCq_CWr/view?usp=sharing

Abstract:

The environmental data managed and made accessible by the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS) are a national asset. Measurements and observations of the environment are fundamental to research in environmental sciences and wider disciplines. They enable trends or patterns to be discovered and/or processes to be better understood. This, in turn, leads to new discoveries, new insights and supports the evidence base which inform many decisions that affect all our lives.

This session will introduce the EDS and its core services, showcase innovation activities and opportunities for feedback from the community.

Topics to be covered:

- Introduction to the EDS and its core services
- End-to-end data pipelines from ingestion to citation to delivery
- Enhanced data services for AI
- Cross disciplinary data solutions to societal challenges
- How we are engaging with the community to shape future services
- Questions

Workshop: Shaping the Future of AI-Ready, User-Driven Environmental Data

Authors: Poppy Townsend (facilitator), Sam Pepler, Carl Watson, Louise Darroch, Alexandra Kokkinaki, Colm Walsh, James Clare, Helen Rawsthorne, Faiza Samreen, Andrew Kingdon, Ag Stephens, Paulius Tvaranavicius, Jesse Alexander

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17494909>

Abstract:

This workshop offers the opportunity to learn more about the Environmental Data Service (following on from the talk). We will explore how we are improving our data to ensure AI and non-specialists are better able to tackle multi-disciplinary environmental challenges.

The workshop will focus on the EDS AMPLIFY project and its end-to-end workflow for environmental sensor data. We have a proof-of-concept service that combines temperature data from multiple data sources (e.g. ship, aircraft, ground-based stations) in near-real time. Upcoming projects will expand the breadth of data that we make available; both sensor data and additional data services (land cover, marine, climate data, satellite data). We would like to explore your views on where we should focus and how we would best ensure users can discover, pick up and use such resources. If you are someone who uses or produces data (especially sensor data) then we'd love to get your views on the work so far and future direction of our roadmap.

The workshop will be a bit like a hackathon but not about coding. We are particularly interested in exploring the possible user journeys of the future. How do you wish you could combine, access, and analyse data from multiple sources or across disciplines? What data services do decisions makers need for cross-sector environmental challenges in line with Government missions? What new tools and techniques are emerging? We'd love to explore your views and needs on these topics. This is your opportunity to have your voice heard on what happens next with our data services.

The workshop will also offer the opportunity for individuals to delve into the technical details (where appropriate) with our team. We hope to identify opportunities for future collaboration.

Exhibition stand

Authors: Poppy Townsend, Rachel Talbot, Charlotte Miskin-Hymas, Hannah Dean, Alysa Fisher

Resources:

Pull up banner - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17551989>

Leaflet - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17552044>

Abstract:

The NERC Environmental Data Service supports anyone with an interest in learning more about the natural world by hosting the largest collection of environmental science data in the UK.

Our main goal is to ensure that environmental data are made available, accessible and re-usable for the long-term in order to fully realise their value.

We advise researchers on how best to prepare data for long term storage and discovery. We engage with users to deliver data in line with their increasingly innovative and cross-disciplinary needs.

Please join us for a chat at our stand if you have questions, feedback, wish to see demonstrations of our work or just want to learn more! Someone from the Environmental Data Service team will be at the stand during the breaks and networking sessions.

References

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